

INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH JOURNAL OF MANAGEMENT SOCIOLOGY & HUMANITIES

ISSN 2277 – 9809 (online)

ISSN 2348 - 9359 (Print)

An Internationally Indexed Peer Reviewed & Refereed Journal

www.IRJMSH.com
www.isarasolutions.com

Published by iSaRa Solutions

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON DIGITALISATION IN THE ORGANISED RETAIL SECTOR IN KERALA

***Dr. Ninikala K.**

* Assistant Professor & Head,

Department of Commerce, Providence Women's College, Kozhikode.

Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic has triggered unprecedented disruptions across industries worldwide, fundamentally altering the way business operate. The retail sector, in particular, experienced significant challenges due to lockdowns, social distancing measures, and shifts in consumer behaviour. To navigate these challenges, many retailers accelerated their adoption of digital technologies to ensure continuity and resilience. This research aims to comprehensively investigate the impact the COVID-19 pandemic on digitalisation within the retail sector, focusing on key areas such as marketing, sales, payment, customer service inventory management, vendor management and customer relationship management (CRM).

Keywords: COVID-19, digitalisation, retail sector.

Introduction

The Digital India initiative is the Government of India's flagship programme. It is an umbrella programme that spans multiple departments. The Digital India Mission's goal is to provide high-speed internet in all Gram Panchayats and easy access to Common Service Centres throughout the country. Digital access, digital commerce, digital communication, digital literacy, digital etiquette, digital law, digital rights and responsibilities, and digital health and wellness are the important components of Digital India. Analysts estimate that the Digital India plan could increase GDP by \$1 trillion by 2025. It has the potential to play a significant role in macroeconomic factors such as GDP growth, job creation, labour productivity, growth in a variety of businesses, and revenue leakages for the government. There are numerous impediments to its successful implementation, including digital illiteracy, poor infrastructure, slow internet speeds, a lack of coordination among various departments, taxation issues, and so on (Cypher Learning).

The concept of digital transformation in retail is based on customer needs and expectations. Retailers consider how they can use technological innovations to discover new ways to drive revenue and develop innovative business models when deciding to go digital. The corona virus attacked the state in the year 2020, and government declared complete lockdown till 31st March in the first stage (Anil Kumar, 2020). Due to the lockdown, retail stores and shopping malls were shuttered, which caused a significant increase in sales for online retailers as people turned to other purchasing options. (Kingson & Jennifer, 2020). Lockdown and social distancing due to pandemic have made changes in the consumer behaviour. This influenced the researcher to conduct a study on the impact of covid-19 on digitalisation in the organised retail sector.

Review of literature

(Tong & Gong, 2020) To increase efficiency and competitiveness, small and medium-sized businesses are increasingly turning to digitalisation. The report examines the state of digitalisation among SMEs and enterprises in Malaysia prior to the pandemic. Although the conventional thinking holds that Covid-19 has ushered in a shift toward digitalisation, SMEs nonetheless face numerous hurdles in doing so. Government and policy interventions can help to facilitate this process, and researchers propose several initiatives that can be implemented to help SME digitalisation.

(Jnr & Petersen, 2021) Enterprises are surviving in a digital transitional society, where strategic alliances are being formed as a result of the constant change during the coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic. The formation of Virtual Enterprises (VE) is a business medium in which firms can share their core competencies in order to thrive in a pandemic. Despite growing interest in VE research, there are still gaps in comprehending the notion of digitization of VE activities during emergencies. This paper evaluated the theoretical underpinning notion of VE digitalization through a review of existing literature and a meta-analysis of 55 VE research articles.

(Yip, Lau, & Nambiar, 2023) The Covid-19 outbreak stopped several companies as governments implemented international travel restrictions on top of a national lockdown. Firm performance was hampered by decreased order and output. The purpose of this study is to see if digitization has lessened the detrimental impact of the Covid-19 outbreak on Malaysia's manufacturing industry. The findings reveal that manufacturing sales performance was negatively associated to the Covid-19 epidemic from January to December 2020, using sales as the performance benchmark for 24 industrial sectors. The negative impact of Covid-19, on the other hand, was reduced by a higher level of digitization. Further research will confirm the mitigating role of digitization. This study was able to quantify Covid-19's moderating effect on manufacturing sectors.

(Dohring, Histrov, Maier, Roeger, & Thyssen, 2021) This article characterizes the conventional and digital sectors of the EU economy since the late 1990s and offers a two-sector growth model that shows structural differences between the two sectors. In comparison to traditional commodities and services, digital goods and services are more easily scalable yet demand more upfront intangible investment. These characteristics need the consideration of fixed costs and a divergence from ideal competition, and they raise concerns regarding market entry.

Statement of the research problem

The retail industry has undergone a significant transformation over the years with the advent of digital technologies. However, the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic in the late 2019 brought unprecedented challenges that accelerated the pace of digitalisation in the retail sector. The pandemic disrupted traditional business models and consumer behaviour, forcing retailers to rapidly adapt and adopt digital solutions to ensure business continuity. This study aims to analyse the multifaced impact of COVID-19 pandemic on digitalisation in the retail sector. Do the Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown influenced the digitalisation initiatives? Are there any changes in the level of impact of covid 19 on digitalisation in food and grocery, apparels and consumer electronics retail sector?

Objectives of the study

- To identify the level of impact of covid-19 on digitalisation in the organised retail sector
- To determine the level of impact of covid-19 on digitalisation of different type of retail unit

Significance of the study

The COVID-19 pandemic had a significant impact on the retail sector, accelerating the pace of digitalisation across various aspects of the industry, including marketing, sales, customer services, payment, inventory management, vendor management, and customer relationship management (CRM). Retailers have shifted their focus to from traditional brick-and-mortar stores to online platforms due to lockdowns and social distancing measures. This has accelerated the adoption of digital marketing strategies, such as social media advertising, influencer partnerships, and email campaigns, to reach customers directly at home. Retailers are increasingly using advanced inventory management systems and real time analytics to optimize stock levels, prevent stockouts, and reduce excess inventory. Contactless payment methods, such as mobile wallets and QR code-based payments, gained significant popularity during the pandemic as customers sought touch-free transactions. Retailers have adapted by expanding their payment options to cater to these preferences. The pandemic led to an increased demand for online customer service solutions. Retailers have invested in virtual shopping assistants, and 24/7 customer support to address the customer queries and concerns promptly. This study gives a clear picture about the level of digitalisation in the organised retail sector in the period prior to covid 19 pandemic and after.

Scope of the study

The Indian retail market is one of the top five retail market in the world in terms of economic value. In India, the retail industry was largely unorganised, consisting of drug stores, medium and small grocery stores. The majority of organised retailing in India has only recently begun and is concentrated primarily in major cities. The expansion of the Indian organised retail market is primarily due to changes in consumer behaviour. This shift has occurred in the consumer as a result of increased income, changing lifestyles, and favourable demographic patterns. The consumer now prefers to shop at a location that offers food, entertainment, and shopping all under one roof. This has significantly boosted the Indian organised retail market (mapsofindia). The study focused on the impact of digitalisation in the organised retail outlets and is limited to state Kerala, as it is the first digital state in the country. As per the retail industry update (RAI, 2020), within the organised retail sector, food and grocery holds 65% of retail sector, Apparel (10%), Consumer electronics (9%), jewellery and accessories (7%), Health & Entertainment (4%), Home décor and furnishing (3%) and Beauty & personal care (2%). It is limited to food & grocery, apparel and consumer electronics; the three major contributors to the organized retail sector. It includes only the retail outlets registered before 2018.

Research Methodology and Data Base

The research work is descriptive in nature. It is descriptive in the light of facts that it describes the characteristic and studies the relationship between the variables. The study is based on both secondary and primary data. Secondary data was collected from journals, conference proceedings,

websites, etc. and primary data was collected from organised retail sector using pre-tested and structured questionnaire.

In order to identify whether the Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown influenced the retail outlets to switch to digital mode, data was collected from the retail outlets on this aspect and the respondents were asked to mark their response in a five-point scale beginning with 1 for not digitalised and 5 for fully digitalised on seven constructs namely marketing, sales, mode of payment, customer service, inventory management, vendor management and customer relationship management. The respondents were asked to mark the digitalisation in the retail outlets of each construct for a period prior to covid pandemic and present digitalisation.

Sample Design

The population of the study consists of organised retail outlets in Kerala. The sample was selected in three different stages. In the first stage, three districts with large number of organised retail outlets were selected i.e., Thiruvananthapuram, Ernakulam and Kozhikode. In the second stage three major contributors in the organised retail sector was selected i.e., Food and grocery retail sector, apparel retail sector and consumer electronics retail sector. And in the third stage a sample of 330 retail outlets were selected using convenient sampling method as the official database of organised retail outlets was not available.

Results & Discussion

Digitalisation prior to covid 19 pandemic in the retail sector is shown in table 1 and digitalisation after covid 19 pandemic is shown in table 2.

Table 1
Digitalisation in the retail sector prior to Covid-19 pandemic

Variables	Digitalisation (in Per cent)				
	Not Digitalised	Partly Digitalised			Fully Digitalised
	1	2	3	4	5
Marketing	53.9	16.1	27.6	0.0	2.4
Sales	67.9	21.8	7.9	0.0	2.4
Mode of Payment	14.2	47.3	38.2	0.0	0.3
Customer service	32.7	30.6	31.5	1.8	3.4
Inventory Management	6.1	16.1	26.4	12.1	39.3
Vendor management	48.8	12.4	28.2	6.1	4.5
Customer Relationship Management	28.5	34.2	29.1	5.8	2.4

Source: Primary Data

Table 2
Digitalisation in the retail sector after Covid-19 pandemic

Variables	Digitalisation (in Per cent)				
	Not Digitalised	Partly Digitalised			Fully Digitalised
	1	2	3	4	5
Marketing	3.9	38.8	24.2	10.0	23.1
Sales	38.8	22.7	25.8	2.4	10.3
Mode of Payment	0.0	0.9	30.0	35.5	33.6
Customer service	0.6	13.0	46.1	21.8	18.5
Inventory Management	0.9	2.1	25.8	27.0	44.2
Vendor management	19.7	20.6	19.4	14.2	26.1
Customer Relationship Management	2.4	6.4	49.7	21.2	20.3

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 shows the digitalisation in the retail sector prior to Covid-19 pandemic. In case of marketing, majority (53.9%) of the retail outlets were not digitalised prior to Covid-19 pandemic and only 2.4% was fully digitalised. In case of sales also majority (67.9%) of the retail outlets are not digitalised prior to Covid-19 pandemic and only 2.4% are fully digitalised. In case of mode of payment, majority of the retail outlets are partly digitalised, 14.2% are not digitalised and only 0.3% is fully digitalised. In case of customer service, majority of the retail outlets are partly digitalised, 32.7% are not digitalised and 3.4% are fully digitalised. Inventory management is partly digitalised prior to covid-19 pandemic, 39.3% are fully digitalised and 6.1% are not digitalised. In case of vendor management, 48.8% of the retail outlets are not digitalised and 4.5% are fully digitalised. In case of customer relationship management, majority of the retail outlets are partly digitalised prior to covid-19 pandemic, 28.5% are not digitalised and 2.4% are fully digitalised.

Table 2 shows the digitalisation in the retail sector after covid-19 lockdown. In case of marketing, majority of the retail outlets are partly digitalised, 23.1% are fully digitalised and 3.9% are not digitalised. In case of sales, majority of the retail outlets are partly digitalised, 38.8% are not digitalised and 10.3% are fully digitalised. It was interesting to note that in case of mode of payment, none of the retail outlets are not digitalised, majority are partly digitalised and 33.6% are fully digitalised. Most of the retail outlets are partly digitalised in case of customer service, 18.5% are fully digitalised and only 0.6% is not digitalised. Inventory management is also partly digitalised, 44.2% are fully digitalised and only 0.9% is not digitalised. Most of the retail outlets are partly digitalised in case of vendor management, 26.1% are fully digitalised and 19.7% are not

digitalised. Customer relationship management is also partly digitalised, only 2.4% is not digitalised and 20.3% of the retail outlets are fully digitalised in this aspect.

Level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation in retail sector

In order to find the level of improvement in digitalisation due to the impact of Covid 19, the respondents are asked to give the range of digitalisation from 1(not digitalised) to 5 (fully digitalised) before and after covid-19 pandemic. On the basis of information provided by the respondents the score was given as 0, 1,2,3,4. The scoring pattern is, if there is no change before and after score is given 0. If there is one level of improvement then the score is given as 1 and so on. Based on this score the analysis is done to establish the objectives. The total score of the 7 questions for all 330 respondents is found out, based on which mean % score of level of level of improvement in digitalisation was calculated $[MPS = \frac{MeanScore \times 100}{Maximumpossiblescore}]$. This score is classified into one of the four groups as low if the mean % score is less than 35%, average if the mean % score is between 35 to 50 per cent, above average if the mean % score lies in the interval 50 to 75% and high if the mean % score is above 75%. A one sample Z test is carried out to test the significance (Loyd & Abidin, 1985).

Table 3
Overall impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation

Variable	N	Mean	S.D.	Mean % score	CV	z	p value
Impact of Covid-19 pandemic	330	7.94	3.93	28.37	49.44	-8.593	<0.001

Source: Primary Data

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation is 28.37% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 on digitalisation is low. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is less than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is significant. Hence, we conclude that the level of impact of Covid-19 on digitalisation is low.

Level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation

Table 4 shows the level of impact of Covid-19 on digitalisation of all the constructs namely marketing, sales, mode of payment, customer service, inventory management, vendor management and customer relationship management.

Table 4
Level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Mean % score	CV	z	P value	Level
Marketing	330	1.28	0.73	32.12	56.47	-2.883	0.004	Low
Sales	330	0.75	0.91	18.86	121.19	-12.822	<0.001	Low
Mode of Payment	330	1.77	0.94	44.24	52.91	7.172	<0.001	Average
Customer service	330	1.32	0.90	33.03	68.05	-1.592	0.112	Low
Inventory Management	330	0.49	0.66	12.20	134.87	-25.181	<0.001	Low
Vendor management	330	1.01	1.12	25.30	110.29	-6.312	<0.001	Low
Customer Relationship Management	330	1.31	0.98	32.80	75.03	-1.622	0.106	Low

Source: Primary Data

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of marketing is 32.12% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of marketing is low. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is less than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is significant.

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of sale is 18.86% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of sales is low. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is less than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is significant.

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of mode of payment is 44.24% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown on digitalisation of mode of payment is average. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is less than 0.05 and Z value is positive, which indicates that the test is significant.

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of customer service is 33.03% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown on digitalisation of customer service is poor. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is greater than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is not significant.

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of inventory management is 12.20% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of inventory management is low. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is less than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is significant. Hence, we conclude that the level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of inventory management is low.

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of vendor management is 25.30% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of vendor management is low. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is less than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is significant. Hence, we conclude that the level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown on digitalisation of vendor management is low.

The mean percentage score of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of customer relationship management is 32.80% which indicate that level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown on digitalisation of customer relationship management is low. The CV indicates that this score is not stable as it is more than 20%. The p value is greater than 0.05 and Z value is negative, which indicates that the test is not significant. Hence, we conclude that the level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of customer relationship management is low.

Comparison of level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation in retail sector

In order to determine the level of impact of Covid-19 pandemic and lockdown on digitalisation of different type of Retail units i.e., Food & Grocery, Apparel and Consumer Electronics, Mean Percentage Score (MPS) was calculated and one sample Z test is carried out to test the significance. The result is shown in table 5.

Table 5
Impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation in retail sector

Type of retail unit	Variables	N	Mean	S.D.	Mean % score	CV	z	p value	Impact level
Food & Grocery	Marketing	110	1.68	0.79	42.05	46.92	3.746	<0.001	Average
	Sales	110	1.31	0.75	32.73	57.37	-1.269	0.207	Low
	Mode of Payment	110	2.21	1.13	55.23	50.97	7.536	<0.001	Above Average
	Customer service	110	1.44	0.92	35.91	64.33	0.413	0.681	Average
	Inventory Management	110	0.50	0.71	12.50	142.71	-13.228	<0.001	Low

	Vendor management	110	1.29	1.40	32.27	108.21	-0.819	0.415	Low
	Customer Relationship Management	110	1.44	1.14	35.91	79.20	0.335	0.738	Average
Apparel	Marketing	110	1.19	0.57	29.77	47.58	-3.871	<0.001	Low
	Sales	110	0.40	0.67	10.00	166.59	-15.739	<0.001	Low
	Mode of Payment	110	1.49	0.62	37.27	41.38	1.545	0.125	Average
	Customer service	110	1.22	0.83	30.45	67.99	-2.303	0.023	Low
	Inventory Management	110	0.54	0.59	13.41	109.14	-15.473	<0.001	Low
	Vendor management	110	1.13	1.04	28.18	92.38	-2.747	0.007	Low
	Customer Relationship Management	110	1.10	0.80	27.50	72.80	-3.929	<0.001	Low
Consumer Electronics	Marketing	110	0.98	0.62	24.55	63.20	-7.069	<0.001	Low
	Sales	110	0.55	1.02	13.86	183.75	-8.702	<0.001	Low
	Mode of Payment	110	1.61	0.84	40.23	51.96	2.623	0.010	Average
	Customer service	110	1.31	0.94	32.73	71.50	-1.019	0.311	Low
	Inventory Management	110	0.43	0.67	10.68	156.79	-15.229	<0.001	Low

Vendor management	110	0.62	0.69	15.45	111.69	-11.876	<0.001	Low
Customer Relationship Management	110	1.40	0.96	35.00	68.55	0.000	1.000	Low

Source: Primary Data

As per the above table, the level of impact of covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation in Food & Grocery sector is above average only for mode of payment, its average in case of marketing, customer service and customer relationship management and its low in sales, inventory management and vendor management. In case of Apparel and Consumer Electronic retail sector, the impact of covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation is low for marketing, sales, customer service, inventory management, vendor management and customer relationship management and average for mode of payment.

Major Findings

- The overall impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation was low. Only in case of mode of payment there was an average impact.
- In case of food and grocery retail outlet, the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation of marketing, customer service and customer relationship management were average but in case of mode of payment there was an above average impact.
- In case of apparel and consumer electronics retail outlet, the impact of Covid-19 pandemic on digitalisation was low in case of marketing, sales, customer service, inventory management, vendor management and customer relationship management but there was an average impact on the mode of payment.

Conclusion

The study sought to examine the overarching impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the digitalisation of the retail sector. The findings reveal a nuanced landscape where the overall impact on digitalisation was observed to be low. However, a more granular examination of individual constructs provided valuable insights. Among the individual constructs evaluated, the mode of payment emerged as a significant factor, with an average impact. This underscores the adaptability and resilience of the retail sector in responding to the challenges posed by the pandemic. Notably, the remaining constructs exhibited a predominantly low impact. This suggests that while the retail sector may have encountered disruptions, the extent of change in these specific areas was comparatively modest.

When comparing the impact across sub-sectors, the mode of payment stood out with an above-average impact in the food and grocery retail sector. This emphasizes a heightened emphasis on digital payment methods in this particular segment. Conversely, the impact on the mode of payment in the apparel and consumer electronics sectors was average, indicating a more uniform

response across these sectors. In other constructs, such as marketing, customer service, and customer relationship management, the impact was consistently average for food and grocery, while it was generally low for consumer electronics and apparel.

Implications for the Retail Industry:

- The findings of this study carry implications for the retail industry as it navigates the evolving landscape post-COVID-19. Recognizing the varying impacts on different constructs and sectors, businesses can tailor their strategies accordingly.
- The observed differences highlight the need for a nuanced and sector-specific approach to digitalization efforts. While the mode of payment emerged as a focal point across sectors, other areas may require targeted interventions to foster digital transformation.

In essence, this study underscores the complexity of the digitalisation journey within the retail sector in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. As the industry continues to adapt, understanding these nuances will be crucial for devising effective strategies and ensuring sustained growth in the digital era.

Bibliography

- Anil Kumar, B. (2020). *Kerala to go under lockdown till March 31*. Kerala: The Times of India. Retrieved from <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/city/thiruvananthapuram/kerala-to-go-under-lockdown-till-march-31/articleshow/74778886.cms>
- Cypher Learning*. (n.d.). Retrieved from Cypher Learning: <https://www.cypherlearning.com/resources/infographics/neo/the-9-elements-of-digital-citizenship-your-students-need-to-know>
- Dohring, B., Histrov, A., Maier, C., Roeger, W., & Thysen, A. T. (2021, September). COVID-19 acceleration in digitalisation, aggregate productivity growth and the functional income distribution. *International Economics and Economics Policy*, 571-604.
- Fuzzi, B., Géring, Z., & Pál, E. S. (2022). Changing expectations related to digitalisation and socialisation in higher education. Horizon scanning of pre- and post-COVID-19 discourses. *Educational Review*, 74(3), 484-516. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131911.2021.2023101>
- jnr, B. A., & Petersen, S. A. (2021). *Examining the digitalisation of virtual enterprises amidst the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic and meta-analysis*. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/17517575.2020.1829075>
- Kingson, & Jennifer, A. (2020). *The coronavirus is causing a slow motion retail apocalypse*. Axios. Retrieved July 6, 2020
- Loyd, B., & Abidin, R. (1985). Revision of the Parent STress Index. *Journal of Pediatric Psychiatry*, 10(2), 169.
- mapsofindia. (n.d.). *Indian Organized Retail Market*. Retrieved from business.mapsofindia.com/india-retail-industry/indian-organized-retail-market.html
- OECD. (n.d.). *Digitalisation and Innovation*. Retrieved from www.oecd.org/g20/topics/digitalisation-and-innovation/
- Tong, A., & Gong, R. (2020, October 20). *The impact of COVID-19 on SME digitalisation in Malaysia*. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=impact+of+covid+on+digitalisation&btnG=
- Yip, T. M., Lau, W. Y., & Nambiar, S. (2023). Has digitalisation mitigated the impact of Covid 19 on the Manufacturing Sector's Performance? *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 4-25.